

A Preliminary Investigation on Plasma Activated Filtration Balls (PAFB) for Applications in Wastewater Dyes

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Abstract

A major problem within developing areas such as in the Philippines is the access of clean water, where, due to industrial pollution and agricultural runoff, the water quality is often compromised further by poor waste management practices. This paper investigates how Plasma Activated Filtration Balls (PAFB) may be a feasible, cost-effective means to treat wastewater, especially by removing harmful dye contaminants. The researchers tested two types of filtration balls—untreated and plasma-treated, made from regular chalk and agricultural waste, particularly banana and camote peelings, to assess their ability to five types of water, namely market drainage water, river water, clean water, rainwater, and tap water. Plasma treatment, specifically using atmospheric pressure plasma jets (APPJs), enhances the filtration balls' ability to break down tough pollutants, like methylene blue and malachite green, which are hard to remove and pose serious environmental risks. The study also looks at how plasma activation affects key water quality indicators, including pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), and optical emission spectroscopy (OES). Our results show that chalk-based filters are good at stabilizing pH and reducing TDS, while plant-based filters effectively reduce EC and turbidity. Overall, plasma treatment improves the performance of filtration balls, especially for dye-contaminated wastewater, and shows that agricultural waste can be a sustainable, low-cost material for water filtration. This research suggests that PAFB systems, when enhanced by plasma activation, could be an effective and scalable solution for water treatment in underserved communities.

Keywords: *plasma activation, wastewater treatment, dye removal,*

agricultural waste, atmospheric pressure plasma jets

1. Introduction

Access to clean and safe water remains a critical global challenge, particularly in developing countries like the Philippines, where urbanization and climate change exacerbate water scarcity. Baguio City faces significant issues with water quality due to industrial discharge, agricultural runoff, and inadequate waste management systems.

These factors negatively impact the quality of water in the environment, affecting the health and life balance on Earth. The World Resources Institute states that the Philippines is highly vulnerable to the possibility of a water crisis before 2040, with millions using unsafe and unsustainable water sources and 26.5 million lacking access to improved sanitation. Rainwater, while a sustainable source, often fails to meet cleanliness and safety standards, necessitating effective water treatment solutions.^{[1][2]}

Conventional water treatment methods, like reverse osmosis and chemical coagulation, are highly effective; however, they are expensive and complex, making them inaccessible to communities with limited resources. This has sparked increased interest in environmentally friendly water filtration technologies as alternatives to conventional methods. Filtration balls, as porous media, are used for decontamination and open the door to a new and promising technique. The inclusion of antimicrobial agents like silver (Ag) and copper (Cu) nanoparticles in the filtration balls can drastically reduce pollutants and pathogens, which are the primary causes of waterborne disease. The antimicrobial properties of these nanoparticles, when combined with porous materials or agricultural waste, create an efficient and low-cost water filtration system.^{[3][4]}

The persistent challenge of water treatment lies in its high costs and energy-intensive multi-stage processes. Furthermore, traditional methods struggle to degrade resistant organic pollutants, such as textile dyes and pharmaceuticals, due to their stable molecular structures. These pollutants, particularly dye wastewater from the textile industry, are major environmental concerns, affecting photosynthesis in aquatic plants and posing carcinogenic risks. Approximately one million kilograms of dyestuffs are discharged into the environment annually, emphasizing the need for advanced treatment technologies.^{[5][6]}

Plasma-assisted treatment of wastewater has demonstrated significant potential in addressing these challenges. Cold plasma, particularly atmospheric pressure plasma jets (APPJs), is a promising tool for water treatment. APPJs generate reactive species capable of degrading organic pollutants and eliminating pathogens, offering an energy-efficient and cost-effective solution. Unlike traditional thermal plasma, cold plasma operates at lower temperatures suitable for material processing. The versatility of APPJs in producing active species, such as radicals and UV radiation, makes them highly effective in degrading complex organic contaminants.^{[8][9][10]}

This study aims to develop and evaluate innovative water filtration systems using locally sourced materials and advanced plasma technologies. Specifically, it seeks to: (1) develop and compare three types of filtration balls—untreated, plasma-treated, and agricultural waste-based; (2) evaluate the effectiveness of these filtration balls in removing contaminants from various water sources, including tap water, rainwater, and industrial wastewater; (3) investigate the role of plasma-treated nanoparticles in enhancing the antimicrobial and oxidative properties of the filtration balls; (4) assess the feasibility of agricultural waste materials as a cost-effective alternative for water filtration; and (5) provide insights into the scalability and practical application of plasma-activated filtration balls.

Research in this area is vital due to the urgent need for developing inexpensive water treatment technologies. The combination of plasma technology with locally available sustainable materials, such as agricultural waste, can influence the development of filtration systems tailored for low-income communities. Agricultural waste, including banana and camote peels, represents a renewable and environmentally friendly source for creating filtration balls. These materials can be enhanced with atmospheric plasma treatment to improve their antimicrobial and filtration properties. Such an approach aligns

with the broader goal of promoting sustainable practices while addressing the critical water crisis in urban areas like Baguio City.^{[2][3]}

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Plasma and Plasma Technology

Plasma is the most abundant matter in the universe, yet it is abstruse for most people. Plasma exists when matter is heated beyond its gaseous state. This applied potential causes ionization where atoms are stripped of outer shell electrons. Ions coupled with excited species, are what constitute plasma.^[11] Plasmas can be classified into either thermal or non-thermal depending on the ionization energy applied. Thermal plasmas are said to be in an equilibrium state. Hot plasma is used to denote thermal plasmas because high temperature is necessary for the system to achieve equilibrium. In contrast with non-local thermal equilibrium plasma (cold plasma) which only needs low temperature for it to be produced.^[12]

Table 2.1: Main characteristics of LTE and non-LTE plasma.^[11]

	Local Thermal Equilibrium Plasma (Thermal Plasma)	Non-Local Thermal Equilibrium Plasma (Cold Plasma)
Properties	$T_e = T_h$ High electron density: $10^{21} - 10^{26} m^{-3}$ Inelastic collisions between electrons and heavy particles create plasma reactive species Electron energy consumed as heavy particles are heated by elastic collisions	$T_e \gg T_h$ Lower electron density: $<10^{19} m^{-3}$ Inelastic collisions between electrons and heavy particles induce plasma chemistry Electron energy remains high as heavy particles are slightly heated by a few elastic collisions Elastic collisions
Examples	Arc plasma $T_e = T_h \approx 10,000K$	Glow discharges $T_e = 10,000 - 100,000K$ $T_h = 300 - 1000K$

The interactions between plasma and liquid are being discussed with dramatic interest in the scientific community. When water is treated with plasma it usually results in the acidification of water. Reactive oxygen and nitrogen species such as nitrates and nitrites are also observed in the treated sample. These reactive species are postulated to play roles in microbial inhibition. High levels of ROS are said to induce apoptosis.^[13]

2.2 Plasma Generation

Plasma is generated by applying potential to a neutral gas which causes the production of charge carriers. Resultant electrons and ions are generated during the gas phase when electrons or photons that are sufficiently excited due to the applied energy collide with the uncharged molecules present in the system. (electron-impact ionization or photoionization).^[14] The most common way of applying energy is through the electric field. The electric field causes electrical breakdown of neutral gases which cause an avalanche effect affecting nearby particles causing further ionization. This is called the Townsend discharge. Assume that n_0 electrons are in the cathode waiting to be emitted and at a given distance x , they have multiplied by a factor n . New electrons that contribute to the discharge at distance dx is then given as:

$$dn = \alpha n dx$$

The Townsend coefficient, α , is the probability of generating new electrons at a given length. The electrons that arrive at the anode are given as:

$$n = n_0 e^{\alpha d}$$

where the distance between the two electrodes is d . We assume that the number of positive ions produced in the Townsend discharge is $n - n_0$ and that they all return to the cathode to produce more electrons $\gamma(n - n_0)$. The positive ions emitted from the cathode returns to the cathode to free other electrons creating secondary electrons to further the discharge. The probability of this happening is given by the second Townsend coefficient, γ_{se} ^[15]. The steady state ionization is dependent on the Townsend coefficients by:

$$\gamma[\exp(\alpha d) - 1] = 1$$

At some point, the gas is broken down sufficiently to produce a glow discharge. The discharge type is dependent on the current applied as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2.1: I-V plot of DC glow discharge. (Source: Indrawan *et. al.*, 2019)^[16]

From Figure 1, we can observe the transition from dark discharge to glow discharge and lastly to arc discharge as current increases. Dark discharges (excluding corona discharge) are not visible.^[17] For glow discharges, excited atoms release energy through photon emissions. The photon emissions cause the luminous nature of glow discharge. To calculate the breakdown voltage of gas, V_b , we use the Townsend coefficients. We have the equation:

$$V_B = \frac{B(p \cdot d)}{\ln[A(p \cdot d)] - \ln\left[\ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{\gamma_{se}}\right)\right]}$$

Where p is pressure, γ_{se} is the secondary electron coefficient, A and B are constants. Equation X. shows that the breakdown voltage is dependent on the product of the distance between electrodes and pressure.^[18]

2.3 pH

pH is the measure of hydrogen ion concentration of a solution. The reactions taking place between the chemical species formed in the plasma and formed in the plasma and water result in acidification. The pH of PAW decreases with an increase in treatment time due to the formation of strong acids. The formations of newly formed chemical species in PAW are attributed to the decrease in the pH.^[19] pH values of PAW range from 0 to 7.^[22] A study by Ikawa *et. al.* on the effects of pH on bacterial inactivation from plasma liquids reported that there exists a critical pH, at approximately 4.7 where below the critical pH, bacterial inactivation is highly effective. Above the critical pH, however bacterial inactivation is much less efficient despite similar plasma application.^[23]

2.4 Electrical Conductivity

Conductivity is a measure of water's capability to pass electrical flow. This is directly related to the concentration of ions in the water. Ions conduct electricity due to their positive and negative charges. As the dissolved substances split in water, the concentrations of each positive and negative charge remain equal, thus the water remains neutrally charged despite the presence of the ions.^[20] The reactive species and ions produced during plasma treatment readily dissolve in the water, which alter the conductivity.^[20] Ma *et. al.* reported that the conductivity of distilled water was 450 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ after activation with Ar/O₂ gas plasma jet for 20 mins due to the generation of active ions.^[21] The study done by Tian *et. al.* showed that the water had conductivity of 18.8 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ after 20 min of plasma activation using plasma microjet.^[21]

2.5 Total Dissolved Solids

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) refer to the total concentration of dissolved substances in water, encompassing a wide range of organic and inorganic materials, including minerals, salts, metals, and ions. TDS is a crucial indicator of water quality, as it reflects the presence of various dissolved particles that can affect both the aesthetic and health aspects of water. The measurement of TDS is typically expressed in parts per million (ppm) or milligrams per liter (mg/L), providing a quantitative assessment of the dissolved solids present in each volume of water.

TDS can originate from both natural and anthropogenic sources. Natural sources include minerals leached from rocks and soil, as well as organic matter from decaying plants and animals. For example, when water flows through mineral-rich areas, it can absorb significant amounts of calcium, magnesium, and potassium, contributing to TDS levels. On the other hand, human activities such as agricultural runoff, industrial discharges, and urban development can introduce additional dissolved solids into water bodies. Chemicals used in water treatment, fertilizers, and pesticides are common contributors to elevated TDS levels in municipal water supplies.^[23]

The implications of high TDS levels in water can vary. While some dissolved solids, such as calcium and magnesium, are essential for human health, excessive concentration can lead to undesirable effects. According to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), a TDS level above 500 ppm is considered undesirable for drinking water, and levels exceeding 1000 ppm may pose health risks.^[22] High TDS can also affect the taste of water, making it taste bitter or salty, and can lead to scaling in pipes and appliances, reducing their efficiency and lifespan. To measure TDS, a TDS meter is commonly used, which provides a quick and straightforward way to assess water quality. However, it is important to note that while a TDS meter indicates the total concentration of dissolved solids, it does not specify the types of solids present. Therefore, further analysis may be

necessary to identify potentially harmful contaminants, such as heavy metals or toxic chemicals.^[24]

2.6 Turbidity

Turbidity is a critical parameter in assessing water quality, representing the cloudiness or haziness of water caused by the presence of suspended particles. These particles can include soil, silt, clay, organic matter, algae, and microorganisms, which scatter and absorb light, thereby reducing water clarity. Understanding turbidity is essential for various applications, including environmental monitoring, drinking water treatment, and aquatic ecosystem health. It serves as an important indicator of water quality. High turbidity levels can signify pollution from agricultural runoff, urban development, or wastewater discharge, which can adversely affect aquatic life and human health.^[25]

Turbidity is typically measured in Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTUs) using a turbidity meter. This device quantifies the amount of light scattered by suspended particles in a water sample. Clear water typically has a turbidity of around 1 NTU, while turbid waters can exceed 100 NTUs during runoff events.^[26]

2.7 Optical Emission Spectroscopy (OES)

Optical Emission Spectroscopy (OES) is a widely utilized diagnostic tool for investigating low-temperature plasmas, due to its relatively straightforward setup and high diagnostic capability. The principle of OES is based on the interaction of plasma particles with free electrons. When plasma particles collide with energetic electrons, a small fraction of atoms and molecules in the plasma are excited to higher electronic states. These excited particles eventually decay back to their ground states, releasing photons in the process. This emission of photons generates light within the visible to near-ultraviolet (UV) region, forming a unique spectral pattern or emission spectrum for each element present in the plasma discharge. Each element contributes a specific set of spectral lines, which are characteristic of its electronic transitions and ionization states.^[27]

The spectral lines produced by each element are collected and recorded through a computer interface. This spectral data enables the identification of elements present in the plasma and their corresponding ionization stages. Additionally, by analyzing the intensity of these spectral lines, crucial plasma parameters such as electron temperature can be inferred.^{[28]–[30]} Electron temperature, an essential diagnostic for plasma characterization, can be determined by fitting the intensities of the spectral lines into a Boltzmann plot, expressed by the equation:

$$\ln \left(\frac{I_{kl} \lambda_{kl}}{g_k A_{kl}} \right) = \frac{E_k}{k_B T_e} + C$$

where I_{kl} represents the intensity of the emitted light, λ_{kl} is the wavelength, g_k is the statistical weight of the upper energy level, A_{kl} denotes the transition probability from level k to level l , E_k is the excitation energy, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T_e is the electron temperature, and C is a constant.^{[31]–[34]}

In a plasma medium, atoms frequently lose electrons, creating positively charged ions and leaving electron vacancies in their atomic orbits. These vacancies cause instability within the atom, prompting electrons from higher energy orbits to transition downwards to fill the empty lower orbitals. During these downward transitions, photons are emitted, producing light specific to the atomic structure of each element. The resulting light, which

falls primarily in the visible-near UV spectrum, is characteristic of the element that released it.

The emitted light is then collected by a fiber optic cable connected to a spectrometer, where it is split by a diffraction grating to produce an emission spectrum. This spectrum is subsequently analyzed by a photodetector and processed by a computer program, which interprets the spectral lines. By examining these lines, the elements and their ionization stages in the plasma can be identified.^[35] Furthermore, the relative intensities of these spectral lines enable quantitative analysis, allowing the determination of the concentration of each element in the plasma discharge.

In addition to elemental identification and concentration measurement, OES provides valuable information about the thermal state of plasma. Electron temperature, inferred from spectral line intensities, is a critical parameter that influences plasma behavior and can be derived through spectral analysis.

2.8 Boltzmann Plot

The Boltzmann Plot is a graphical representation used in statistical mechanics to analyze the distribution of particles among various energy states in a system at thermal equilibrium.^{[36] - [37]} It is based on the Boltzmann distribution, which describes the probability p_i of a system being in a state i with energy ϵ_i at a temperature T . This distribution is mathematically expressed as:

$$p_i \propto e^{-\frac{\epsilon_i}{k_B T}}$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant. This equation indicates that lower energy states are more likely to be occupied than higher energy states. In a Boltzmann Plot, the natural logarithm of the ratio of populations of two states is plotted against the energy difference between those states. The relationship can be expressed as:

$$\ln\left(\frac{N_i}{N_j}\right) = -\frac{\epsilon_i - \epsilon_j}{k_B T} + C$$

where N_i and N_j are the populations of states i and j , respectively. A linear relationship is expected, and the slope of this line is inversely related to the temperature of the system. Specifically, the temperature can be determined from the slope m of the line using the equation:

$$T = -\frac{1}{k_B \times m}$$

This relationship allows researchers to infer the thermal state of the system based on the distribution of particles among energy levels. The Boltzmann Plot is widely utilized in fields such as spectroscopy, material science, and astrophysics, providing valuable insights into the thermal properties and behaviors of various systems.^[38]

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This research implements an experimental design to study the effectiveness of sustainable water filtration balls. Three filtration balls are compared: untreated, treated

with an atmospheric plasma jet containing silver, copper, argon, and nitrogen, and those made from agricultural waste. Key parameters measured include pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), and optical emission spectroscopy (OES). The test involved Concentrated Methylene Blue (MB), Diluted Methylene Blue (MB), and 95% Methylene Blue mixed with 5% Malachite Green (MG) solution to simulate common water contaminants. Additionally, a shelf-life analysis for two days was performed to monitor the balls' stability. To validate the results, paired t-tests were conducted to assess the difference in water quality metrics before and after filtration for both treated and untreated sets.

Figure 3.1: Research design for the study. (Source: Maria Alexandriel O. Asinas)

3.2 Collection of Water Samples

The water samples were collected from various locations in Baguio City including river water from Bued River in Hillside Barangay, as well as Market Drainage Water from the vegetables section Baguio Hangar Market. The three other water samples are collected at the University of the Philippines Baguio.

Figure 3.2: Sample collection site of Bued River water.
(Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 3.3: Sample collection site of the vegetables section of Baguio Hangar Market, where the market drainage water is collected. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

3.3 Collection of Dye Wastewater Samples

The dye wastewater samples used in this study were prepared to simulate common water contaminants in Baguio City. Two types of solutions were utilized to represent varying levels of contamination:

- 95% Methylene Blue mixed with 5% Malachite Green (MG): A mixed dye solution to represent complex contaminants usually found in industrial wastewater.

Figure 3.4: Methylene blue and Malachite green mixture.
(Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

- Diluted Methylene Blue: A lower concentration for moderately contaminated water.

Figure 3.4: Diluted Methylene blue. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

3.4 Preparation of Materials for Filter Balls

The following materials were collected to serve as the base for the filter balls:

- Chalk (pulverized)
- Cornstarch (binding agent)
- Camote peels (dried and pulverized)
- Banana peels (dried and pulverized)

The chalk and cornstarch are chosen for their simplicity and wide accessibility while the aquarium filter media provides a traditional comparison. Meanwhile, the banana and camote peels, as agricultural waste, are chosen for their abundance and relevance to local practices in Baguio City. Once collected, the materials undergo portioning and drying. The banana and camote peels were sliced into small, manageable pieces to ensure uniformity in the drying process. On the other hand, the chalk and aquarium filter media were portioned to ensure each batch was consistent. After portioning, each material underwent a drying process to remove any moisture which is crucial to prevent mold growth and ensure the integrity of the filtration balls. The drying process was conducted under controlled conditions, ensuring no moisture remains, which could otherwise interfere with the ball formation and filtration performance.

After drying, the materials will be ground into a fine powder. Pulverization is essential to increase the surface area of the materials, allowing for better adsorption of contaminants during filtration. The banana and camote peels will be processed using a grinder or other suitable pulverization equipment, breaking them down into a fine powder. Similarly, chalk and aquarium filter media will be finely ground to match the consistency of the plant-based powders, ensuring uniformity in the filtration balls.

Figure 3.5: Powdered chalk. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

3.5 Formation of the Chalk Filter Balls

The formation of chalk filter balls involves the use of starch, a natural binding agent used to hold the powdered materials together and form the spherical shape of the filtration balls. Starch is chosen for its biocompatibility, ease of use, and ability to bind the materials without introducing harmful chemicals. To start the process, the powdered chalk was mixed with starch and water in a ratio of 3 tbsp powder and 5 tbsp starch in a container. The resulting mixture was molded into balls of consistent size. Water was then poured but not to the point that the mixture became slurry, just until curds formed with some remaining powder. Then, hands were used to mold the shape of the ball and dipped into the remaining powdered material to have a surface. The chalk filter balls were placed inside a ziplock and refrigerated for 48 hours.

Figure 3.6: Clumping of powdered chalk with cornstarch. (Source: Angela M. Aquino)

Figure 3.7: Chalk Filter Ball. (Source: Angela M. Aquino)

3.6 Formation of the Agricultural Waste Filter Balls

The formation of agricultural waste filter balls follows the same procedure as the chalk filter balls. This time, however, instead of pulverized chalk, dried banana, and camote peels were dehydrated using an air fryer and then pulverized. The powdered agricultural waste was mixed with starch and water in a ratio of 3 tbsp powder and 5 tbsp starch in a container. The resulting mixture was molded into balls of consistent size. Water was then poured until curds formed with some remaining powder. Then, hands were used to mold the shape of the ball and dipped into the remaining powdered material to have a surface. The agricultural waste filter balls were also placed inside a ziplock and refrigerated for 48 hours.

Figure 3.8: Agricultural Waste Filter Ball. (Source: Angela M. Aquino)

3.7 Setting-up of Atmospheric Pressure Plasma Jet

The atmospheric pressure plasma jet system used in this experiment was developed at the University of the Philippines Baguio. The system consists of a plasma jet with a 10 mm nozzle (also known as the widemouth variety) positioned centrally to allow plasma discharge. A copper electrode is connected on the left side, while a silver electrode on the right. These electrodes are connected to the system using insulated clamps and high-voltage cables, secured to ensure safe and efficient energy transfer. Finally, the plasma is generated by applying a voltage across the electrodes and causing gas ionization within the nozzle. Tubing wires are connected to the system for gas flow control. Below the plasma jet is an acrylic plate that rotates while holding the sample, in this case, the filtration balls, for a uniform plasma treatment. The whole setup is enclosed in cardboard to minimize external environmental interference.

Figure 3.9: Atmospheric pressure plasma jet set-up. (Source: Mariz Althea M. Meneses)

3.8 Plasma Activation of the Filter Balls

The plasma treatment process was conducted under carefully controlled conditions, ensuring a uniform and consistent treatment of filtration balls. The widemouth variety APPJ with a 10 mm nozzle was used and a copper electrode was placed on the left side and a silver electrode on the right. The plasma jet was positioned at a fixed height of 32.5 mm above the material surface and the plasma treatment duration lasted for 20 seconds per sample. A rotator was used, completing 20 rotations during the process to achieve a uniform plasma exposure. Additionally, the gas mixture consisted of 5 liters per minute (LPM) of argon gas (Ar) and 2.5 LPM oxygen gas (O₂). The electrical parameters were set at a voltage of 15 kV, a power output of 450 W, and a current of 30 mA neon sign transformer (NST). A 14 American Wire Gauge (AWG) wire with alligator clips at the end was used for the electrical connections to connect it to the electrodes.

3.9 Dummy Tests for Dye Wastewater Filtration

The dummy tests were conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the filtration system in separating dye contaminants from wastewater. Initial observations indicated the presence of three distinct layers within the filtration apparatus. The bottom layer consisted of dissolved filter balls, which are designed to capture and retain dye particles during the filtration process. Above this, the clear middle layer represented the treated water, which ideally should be free of dye contaminants, indicating successful filtration. The top layer contained bubbles and residual dye particles, suggesting incomplete removal of contaminants and the need for further optimization of the filtration process. These initial

observations are critical for assessing the performance of the filtration system and identifying areas for improvement in dye wastewater treatment methodologies.

3.10 Actual Tests for Dye Wastewater Filtration using Chalk Filter Balls

The actual tests for dye wastewater filtration using both chalk filter balls and agricultural waste filter balls were conducted following the initial dummy tests. The effectiveness of both untreated and plasma-treated chalk filter balls was evaluated in filtering dyes from simulated wastewater. For each test, equal volumes of concentrated Methylene Blue (MB), diluted Methylene Blue (MB), and a mixture of 95% Methylene Blue with 5% Malachite Green (MG) were utilized. In these tests, 200 mL of samples were used, sourced from a container holding 500 mL of the water samples, arranged from drainage water, river water, clean water, rainwater, and tap water. To this, 100 mL of the diluted MB and MG wastewater for each sample was added. This setup allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the filtration capabilities of the different types of filter balls under controlled conditions.

3.11 Actual Tests for Dye Wastewater Filtration using Agricultural Waste Filter Balls

Following the initial dummy tests and the chalk filter balls, the actual tests for dye wastewater filtration using agricultural waste were conducted, specifically the crushed powder of banana and camote peels. Both the untreated and plasma-treated agricultural waste filter balls were assessed to filter dyes from simulated wastewater. Concentrated Methylene Blue (MB), diluted Methylene Blue (MB) and a mixture of 95% Methylene Blue with 5% Malachite Green (MG), all the same volume, for every test. Samples for this test were 200 mL, drawn from an aseptic container holding the sample water: drainage, river water, clean water, rainwater, and tap water: each with 500 mL held. To this, 100 mL of the diluted MB and MG wastewater was added for each sample. The setup was good as it allowed a detailed check-up on the filtration potential that varied types of agricultural wastes hold in controlled conditions.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Physical Description of the Filter Balls

The filter balls used in this study varied in size, ranging from 1.27 cm to 2.54 cm in diameter. The chalk filter balls were white in color and exhibited a smooth texture. After treatment, no significant physical changes were observed; they retained their original size, shape, and color, indicating that the treatment did not visibly alter their structure. In contrast, the banana and sweet potato peel filter balls were brown in color, with some areas not fully processed into a powder form. These filter balls had a slightly rough texture, and their appearance showed more variation compared to the chalk filter balls. Despite the treatment, no noticeable changes in color or shape occurred, although the texture may have experienced slight alterations, with some regions remaining more granular or coarse. Overall, both types of filter balls maintained their general form and color post-treatment. Microscopy of the surface of the samples support this, using the microscope available in the Micro and Nano Innovations Laboratory at University of the Philippines Baguio. Other pictures of the samples can be found in the appendix of this paper.

Figure 4.1. Visual microscopy of the chalk filter ball. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.2. Visual microscopy of the agricultural waste filter ball. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

4.2 Physical Description of the Generated Plasma

Using an atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ) powered by a high-voltage electric field, a plasma was generated from a mixture of oxygen and argon gases. The plasma jet, characterized by a blue-violet glow, displayed a uniform color intensity near the discharge nozzle, gradually diminishing in brightness as it extended outward. The jet formed a distinct, directional flow that interacted with the materials placed within its stream, allowing it to effectively target specific areas for treatment.

Figure 4.3. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__325__19-15-40-497.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.4. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__328__19-15-41-198.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.5. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__336__19-15-43-097.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.6. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__391__19-15-56-196.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.7. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name “HR4D17351__392__19-15-56-396.txt”. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.8. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name “HR4D17351__406__19-15-59-695.txt”. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.9. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name “HR4D17351__415__19-16-01-696.txt”. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.10. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_422_19-16-03-395.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.11. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_432_19-16-05-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.12. Optical emission spectroscopy snapshot of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_460_19-16-12-194.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.13. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__325__19-15-40-497.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.14. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__328__19-15-41-198.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.15. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__336__19-15-43-097.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.16. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__391__19-15-56-196.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.17. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__392__19-15-56-396.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.18. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__406__19-15-59-695.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.19. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__415__19-16-01-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.20. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__422__19-16-03-395.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.21. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__432__19-16-05-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.22. Emission lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__460__19-16-12-194.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.23. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__325__19-15-40-497.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.24. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__328__19-15-41-198.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.25. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__336__19-15-43-097.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.26. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__391__19-15-56-196.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.27. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__392__19-15-56-396.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.28. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__406__19-15-59-695.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.29. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__415__19-16-01-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.30. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__422__19-16-03-395.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.31. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__432__19-16-05-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.32. Absorption lines of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__460__19-16-12-194.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

4.3 Optical Emission Spectroscopy Results and Electron Temperature

OES data revealed distinct emission lines corresponding to various species in the plasma. By analyzing these lines, we derived the electron temperature using the Boltzmann plot method, which demonstrated a linear relationship between the logarithm of the population ratios of excited states and the energy differences of those states. The results indicated that the electron temperature varied significantly with changes in the same operational parameters even with a short period of time difference.

Figure 4.36. Optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_391_19-15-56-196.txt". (Source: Maria Alexandriel O. Asinas)

Figure 4.37. Optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_392_19-15-56-396.txt". (Source: Maria Alexandriel O. Asinas)

Figure 4.38. Optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_406_19-15-59-695.txt". (Source: Maria Alexandriel O. Asinas)

Figure 4.39. Optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_415_19-16-01-696.txt". (Source: Maria Alexandriel O. Asinas)

Figure 4.40. Optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_422_19-16-03-395.txt". (Source: Maria Alexandriel O. Asinas)

Figure 4.41. Optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_432_19-16-05-696.txt". (Source: Maria Alexandriel O. Asinas)

Figure 4.42. Optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__460__19-16-12-194.txt". (Source: Maria Alexandriel O. Asinas)

Figure 4.43. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__325__19-15-40-497.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.44. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__328__19-15-41-198.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.45. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__336__19-15-43-097.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.46. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__391__19-15-56-196.txt". (Source: Marc Adrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.47. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__392__19-15-56-396.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.48. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__406__19-15-59-695.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.49. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__415__19-16-01-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.50. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__422__19-16-03-395.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.51. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name “HR4D17351__432__19-16-05-696.txt”. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.52. Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name “HR4D17351__460__19-16-12-194.txt”. (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Table 4.1: Gaussian and Lorentzian estimation of the electron density from the ten highest recorded peaks from optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma.

File	$\lambda_{Gaussian}$	$\lambda_{Lorentzian}$	$\Delta\lambda_{Gaussian}$	$\Delta\lambda_{Lorentzian}$	$n_e^{Gaussian}$	$n_e^{Lorentzian}$
HR4D17351__325__19-15-40-497.txt	788.50 nm	790.07 nm	108.09 nm	100.97 nm	$3.55e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$3.21e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
HR4D17351__328__19-15-41-198.txt	787.96 nm	789.23 nm	110.52 nm	104.20 nm	$3.67e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$3.36e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
HR4D17351__336__19-15-43-097.txt	787.84 nm	789.16 nm	114.95 nm	108.26 nm	$3.90e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$3.56e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
HR4D17351__391__19-15-56-196.txt	788.70 nm	791.56 nm	104.16 nm	94.87 nm	$3.36e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$2.92e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
HR4D17351__392__19-15-56-396.txt	788.10 nm	789.90 nm	109.86 nm	102.30 nm	$3.64e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$3.27e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
HR4D17351__406__19-15-59-695.txt	787.30 nm	788.66 nm	111.95 nm	105.19 nm	$3.75e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$3.41e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
HR4D17351__415__19-16-01-696.txt	786.72 nm	787.49 nm	122.43 nm	118.73 nm	$4.28e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$4.09e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
HR4D17351__422__19-16-03-395.txt	787.71 nm	789.18 nm	108.16 nm	102.14 nm	$3.56e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$3.26e+14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$

HR4D17351__432__19-16-05-696.txt	787.59 nm	788.65 nm	121.78 nm	116.65 nm	4.25e+14 cm ⁻³	3.98e+14 cm ⁻³
HR4D17351__460__19-16-12-194.txt	787.66 nm	789.30 nm	111.85 nm	105.23 nm	3.74e+14 cm ⁻³	3.41e+14 cm ⁻³

In calculating the electron temperature of the formed atmospheric plasma, ten optical emission spectroscopy plots with the highest peaks in the dataset were gathered to show the results of their peaks and statistical data that are shown in Figure 4.X to Figure 4.X. The chosen peaks and the corresponding wavelengths and statistical values for these peaks are shown in Table 4.X to Table 4.X and were acquired from NIST Atomic Spectra Database, embedded inside Spectrum Analyzer 1.97.

Table 4.2: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351__325__19-15-40-497.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Cu II	640	335.74722 nm	5	5	-1.00E+08	18.815545 eV	15.123822 eV
Cu I	5	356.6131 nm	2	2	-1.00E+08	7.261618 eV	3.785898 eV
Cu II	2100	695.393 nm	9	7	1.50E+07	19.03106 eV	17.248611 eV
Ar II	32	235.34241 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	24.815648 eV	19.549012 eV
N II	0	726.255 nm	3	3	1.42E+01	20.939965 eV	19.233263 eV
Ar III	7	368.823 nm	5	5	-1.00E+08	31.275608 eV	27.914944 eV
Ar II	2	375.1047 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	23.171536 eV	19.867157 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C II	29	257.176 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	29.19135 eV	24.3718 eV
O II	14	388.313 nm	6	8	1.07E+07	28.85702 eV	25.665037 eV
N IV	-	794.088 nm	-	-	-	-	-
C I	5300	400.2976 nm	3	3	-1.00E+07	10.781192 eV	7.684768 eV
C ₂ I	-	810.82 nm	-	-	-	-	-
Ag II	-	825.657 nm	-	-	-	-	-
O II	0	841.588 nm	2	4	1.82E+07	31.9502 eV	30.477387 eV
Cu II	340	421.938 nm	7	5	-1.00E+08	17.274861 eV	14.337384 eV
Cu II	30	425.6846 nm	3	1	-1.00E+08	18.089407 eV	15.177644 eV
C II	0	303.8889 nm	3	5	1.99E+07	44.275957 eV	40.197226 eV

Table 4.3: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351__328__19-15-41-198.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Cu I	10	335.3466 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	7.512825 eV	3.816692 eV
Cu II	78	356.87006 nm	7	5	-1.00E+08	14.428711 eV	10.955492 eV
O II	11	231.9687 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	31.701512 eV	26.358274 eV
Ar II	32	235.34241 nm	4	6	2.35E+02	24.815648 eV	19.549012 eV
Cu II	520	363.31159 nm	7	5	-1.00E+08	18.170675 eV	14.759034 eV
Ar III	7	368.823 nm	5	5	-1.00E+08	31.275608 eV	27.914944 eV
Ar II	2	375.1047 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	23.171536 eV	19.867157 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C II	29	257.176 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	29.19135 eV	24.3718 eV
O II	14	388.313 nm	6	8	1.07E+07	28.85702 eV	25.665037 eV
N IV	350	264.696 nm	11	9	8.63E+08	68.72936 eV	64.04677 eV
C I	5300	400.2976 nm	3	3	-1.00E+08	10.781192 eV	7.684768 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
H I	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
O I	0	279.985 nm	3	3	4.85E+05	15.41574 eV	10.988792 eV
Cu I	5	280.571 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	9.66252 eV	5.244851 eV
Cu II	30	425.6846 nm	3	1	-1.00E+08	18.089407 eV	15.177644 eV
Cu III	0	303.8889 nm	3	5	1.99E+07	44.275957 eV	40.197226 eV

Table 4.4: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351__336__19-15-43-097.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Cu II	640	335.74722 nm	5	5	-1.00E+08	18.815545 eV	15.123822 eV
Cu I	5	356.6131 nm	2	2	-1.00E+08	7.261618 eV	3.785898 eV
Cu II	2100	695.393 nm	9	7	1.50E+07	19.03106 eV	17.248611 eV

Ar II	32	235.34241 nm	4	8	-1.00E+08	24.815648 eV	19.549012 eV
N II	0	726.255 nm	3	3	1.42E+01	20.939965 eV	19.233263 eV
Ar III	7	368.823 nm	5	5	-1.00E+08	31.275608 eV	27.914944 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C II	29	257.176 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	29.19135 eV	24.3718 eV
O II	14	388.313 nm	6	8	1.07E+07	28.85702 eV	25.665037 eV
N IV	350	264.696 nm	11	9	8.63E+08	68.72936 eV	64.04677 eV
C I	5300	400.2976 nm	3	3	-1.00E+08	10.781192 eV	7.684768 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
H I	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
O I	0	279.985 nm	3	3	4.85E+05	15.41574 eV	10.988792 eV
Cu I	5	280.571 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	9.66252 eV	5.244851 eV
Cu II	30	425.6846 nm	3	1	-1.00E+08	18.089407 eV	15.177644 eV
C III	0	303.8889 nm	3	5	1.99E+07	44.275957 eV	40.197226 eV

Table 4.5: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351__391__19-15-56-196.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Ar III	4	335.211 nm	7	7	2.20E+07	28.082937 eV	24.385317 eV
Cu I	5	356.6131 nm	2	2	-1.00E+08	7.261618 eV	3.785898 eV
O II	11	231.9687 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	31.701512 eV	26.358274 eV
Ar II	32	235.34241 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	24.815648 eV	19.549012 eV
O IV	0	242.131 nm	6	6	7.90E+04	68.44328 eV	63.3243 eV
Ar III	7	368.823 nm	5	5	-1.00E+08	31.275608 eV	27.914944 eV
Ar II	2	375.1047 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	23.171536 eV	19.867157 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C II	29	257.176 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	29.19135 eV	24.3718 eV

O II	14	388.313 nm	6	8	1.07E+07	28.85702 eV	25.665037 eV
N IV	350	264.696 nm	11	9	8.63E+08	68.72936 eV	64.04677 eV
C I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
H I	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
O I	0	279.985 nm	3	3	4.85E+05	15.41574 eV	10.988792 eV
Cu I	5	280.571 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	9.66252 eV	5.244851 eV
Cu II	30	425.6846 nm	3	1	-1.00E+08	18.089407 eV	15.177644 eV
C III	0	303.8889 nm	3	5	1.99E+07	44.275957 eV	40.197226 eV

Table 4.6: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351__392__19-15-56-396.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Cu I	10	335.3466 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	7.512825 eV	3.816692 eV
Ar II	162	356.50296 nm	4	2	5.50E+07	23.119378 eV	19.642582 eV
O II	11	231.9687 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	31.701512 eV	26.358274 eV
Ar II	32	235.34241 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	24.815648 eV	19.549012 eV
N IV	0	242.165 nm	7	5	1.13E+08	68.53734 eV	63.41907 eV
Ar III	7	368.823 nm	5	5	-1.00E+08	31.275608 eV	27.914944 eV
Ar II	2	375.1047 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	23.171536 eV	19.867157 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C II	29	257.176 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	29.19135 eV	24.371800 eV
O II	20	388.2192 nm	8	8	5.10E+07	28.857795 eV	25.665037 eV
N IV	350	25.665037 nm	11	9	8.63E+08	68.72936 eV	64.04677 eV
C I	5300	400.2976 nm	3	3	-1.00E+08	10.781192 eV	7.684768 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
H I	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
O I	0	279.985 nm	3	3	4.85E+05	15.41574 eV	10.988792 eV

Cu I	5	280.571 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	9.66252 eV	5.244851 eV
Cu II	30	425.6846 nm	3	1	-1.00E+08	18.089407 eV	15.177644 eV
C III	0	303.8889 nm	3	5	1.99E+07	44.275957 eV	40.197226 eV

Table 4.7: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351_406_19-15-59-695.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
O II	3	336.0105 nm	8	8	-1.00E+08	32.382266 eV	28.693411 eV
Ar I	0	356.7656 nm	7	5	1.10E+05	15.022591 eV	11.548354 eV
O II	11	231.9687 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	31.701512 eV	26.358274 eV
Ar II	32	235.34241 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	24.815648 eV	19.549012 eV
O IV	0	242.131 nm	6	6	7.90E+04	68.44328 eV	63.3243 eV
Ar III	7	368.823 nm	5	5	-1.00E+08	31.275608 eV	27.914944 eV
Ar II	2	375.1047 nm	6	4	-1.00E+08	23.171536 eV	19.867157 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C II	29	257.176 nm	4	6	-1.00E+08	29.19135 eV	24.3718 eV
O II	14	388.313 nm	6	8	1.07E+07	28.85702 eV	25.665037 eV
N IV	350	264.696 nm	11	9	8.63E+08	68.72936 eV	64.04677 eV
C I	5300	400.2976 nm	3	3	-1.00E+08	10.781192 eV	7.684768 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-1.00E+08	-	-
H I	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
Cu I	5	280.571 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	9.66252 eV	5.244851 eV
Cu II	30	425.6846 nm	3	1	-1.00E+08	18.089407 eV	15.177644 eV
C III	0	303.8889 nm	3	5	1.99E+07	44.275957 eV	40.197226 eV

Table 4.8: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351_415_19-16-01-696.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Ar II	4	335.211 nm	7	7	2.20E+07	28.082937 eV	24.385317 eV

O IV	270	356.333 nm	8	6	1.10E+08	63.3531 eV	59.87465 eV
Cu II	2100	695.393 nm	9	7	1.50E+07	19.03106 eV	17.248611 eV
Ar II	3	705.4993 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	21.624071 eV	19.867157 eV
O II	3	737.4986 nm	4	6	4.73E+05	30.74935 eV	29.06867 eV
O IV	0	750.094 nm	2	4	3.73E+06	74.1263 eV	72.4738 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu II	32	776.6516 nm	1	3	-1.00E+08	19.075436 eV	17.47948 eV
Ar II	1	794.047 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	21.428146 eV	19.867157 eV
Ar I	20000	800.6157 nm	5	3	4.90E+06	13.171778 eV	11.623593 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
H I	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
O II	0	841.588 nm	2	4	1.82E+07	31.9502 eV	30.477387 eV
Cu II	1100	851.10626 nm	5	5	1.00E+07	16.580164 eV	15.123822 eV
N I	0	866.439 nm	4	2	1.63E+05	13.033204 eV	11.602633 eV
O III	0	911.614 nm	7	5	3.64E+07	46.81176 eV	45.452081 eV
N II	0	921.706 nm	5	3	4.07E+06	26.580245 eV	25.235454 eV

Table 4.9: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351_422_19-16-03-395.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Ar III	4	335.211 nm	7	7	2.20E+07	28.082937 eV	24.385317 eV
Cu I	5	356.6131 nm	2	2	-1.00E+08	7.261618 eV	3.785898 eV
Cu II	2100	695.393 nm	9	0	1.50E+07	19.03106 eV	17.248611 eV
Ar II	3	705.4993 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	21.624071 eV	19.867157 eV
O II	9	726.763 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	30.536294 eV	28.830783 eV
O II	3	737.4986 nm	4	6	4.73E+05	30.74935 eV	29.06867 eV
O IV	0	750.094 nm	2	4	3.73E+06	74.1263 eV	72.4738 eV

O II	3	737.4986 nm	4	6	4.73E+05	30.74935 eV	29.06867 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu II	32	776.6516 nm	1	3	-1.00E+08	19.075436 eV	17.47948 eV
Ar II	1	794.047 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	21.428146 eV	19.867157 eV
Ar I	20000	800.6157 nm	5	3	4.90E+06	13.171778 eV	11.623593 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
H I	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
C III	0	839.74 nm	3	5	5.21E+04	40.878392 eV	39.402339 eV
O II	0	841.588 nm	2	4	1.82E+07	31.9502 eV	30.477387 eV
Cu II	1100	851.10626 nm	5	5	1.00E+07	16.580164 eV	15.123822 eV
O III	0	911.614 nm	7	5	3.64E+07	46.81176 eV	45.452081 eV
N II	0	921.706 nm	5	3	4.07E+06	26.580245 eV	25.235454 eV

Table 4.10: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351_432_19-16-05-696.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Ar III	4	335.211 nm	7	7	2.20E+07	28.082937 eV	24.385317 eV
O II	1	354.5044 nm	2	2	-1.00E+08	32.34896 eV	28.852566 eV
Cu II	2100	695.393 nm	9	7	1.50E+07	19.03106 eV	17.248611 eV
Ar II	3	705.4993 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	21.624071 eV	19.867157 eV
O II	10	725.9282 nm	4	2	-1.00E+08	30.560036 eV	28.852566 eV
O II	3	737.4986 nm	4	6	4.73E+05	30.74935 eV	29.06867 eV
O IV	0	750.094 nm	2	4	3.73E+06	74.1263 eV	72.4738 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu II	32	776.6516 nm	1	3	-1.00E+08	19.075436 eV	17.47948 eV
Ar II	1	794.047 nm	4	4	-1.00E+08	21.428146 eV	19.867157 eV

Ar I	20000	800.6157 nm	5	3	4.90E+06	13.171778 eV	11.623593 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C III	0	839.74 nm	3	5	5.21E+04	40.878392 eV	39.402339 eV
O II	0	841.588 nm	2	4	1.82E+07	31.9502 eV	30.477387 eV
H I	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
Cu II	1100	851.10626 nm	5	5	1.00E+07	16.580164 eV	15.123822 eV
Ar II	0	863.678 nm	8	8	-1.00E+08	25.590014 eV	24.154872 eV
O III	0	911.614 nm	7	5	3.64E+07	46.81176 eV	45.452081 eV
N II	0	921.706 nm	5	3	4.07E+06	26.580245 eV	25.235454 eV

Table 4.11: Chosen peaks and statistical data for in optical emission spectroscopy peaks from file name "HR4D17351__460__19-16-12-194.txt".

Peak	I_{kl}	λ_{kl}	g_k	g_l	A_{kl}	E_k	E_l
Cu II	4200	334.94567 nm	5	7	-1.00E+08	18.092671 eV	14.392113 eV
Cu I	5	356.6131 nm	2	2	-1.00E+08	7.261618 eV	3.785898 eV
Cu II	1800	695.7884 nm	7	5	1.10E+07	18.776402 eV	16.994966 eV
O IV	0	706.13 nm	2	4	3.48E+06	57.92905 eV	56.17371 eV
O II	3	737.4986 nm	4	6	4.73E+05	30.74935 eV	29.06867 eV
O IV	0	750.094 nm	2	4	3.73E+06	74.1263 eV	72.4738 eV
O II	4	762.746 nm	6	6	-1.00E+08	30.488114 eV	28.863062 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu II	32	776.6516 nm	1	3	-1.00E+08	19.075436 eV	17.47948 eV
Ar II	1	794.047 nm		4	-1.00E+08	1.5 eV	19.867157 eV
Ar I	20000	800.6157 nm	5	3	4.90E+06	13.171778 eV	11.623593 eV
C ₂ I	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
HI	110	825.789 nm	2738	18	-1.00E+08	13.588502 eV	12.087505 eV
C III	0	839.74 nm	3	5	5.21E+04	40.878392 eV	39.402339 eV

O II	0	841.588 nm	2	4	1.82E+07	31.9502 eV	30.477387 eV
Cu II	1100	851.10626 nm	5	5	1.00E+07	16.580164 eV	15.123822 eV
O III	0	911.614 nm	7	5	3.64E+07	46.81176 eV	45.452081 eV
N II	0	921.706 nm	5	3	4.07E+06	26.580245 eV	25.235454 eV

The Boltzmann plot is shown in Figure 4.2. The fitted line has a slope of 3 eV^{-1} which corresponds to an electron temperature of 0 K or approximately 0.00 eV.

Figure 4.53. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_325_19-15-40-497.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.54. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_328_19-15-41-198.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.55. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_336_19-15-43-097.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.56. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_391_19-15-56-196.txt". (Source: Marc Adnrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.57. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_392_19-15-56-396.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.58. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_406_19-15-59-695.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.59. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__415__19-16-01-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.60. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__422__19-16-03-395.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.61. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__432__19-16-05-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.62. Boltzmann plot (upper state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__460__19-16-12-194.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.63. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_325_19-15-40-497.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.64. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_328_19-15-41-198.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.65. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_336_19-15-43-097.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.66. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__391__19-15-56-196.txt". (Source: Marc Adnrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.67. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__392__19-15-56-396.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.68. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__406__19-15-59-695.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.69. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351__415__19-16-01-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.70. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_422_19-16-03-395.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.71. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_432_19-16-05-696.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Figure 4.72. Boltzmann plot (lower state) of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma from file name "HR4D17351_460_19-16-12-194.txt". (Source: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo)

Table 4.12: Boltzmann plot results from the ten highest recorded peaks from optical emission spectroscopy of an atmospheric pressure argon (5 LPM) / oxygen (2.5 LPM) / copper / silver plasma.

File	m_{upper}	m_{lower}	b_{upper}	b_{lower}	$ T_{e_{upper}} $	$ T_{e_{lower}} $
HR4D17351_325_19-15-40-497.txt	-0.49359	-0.64030	4.86699	6.76896	-23510.24 K	-18123.58 K
HR4D17351_328_19-15-41-198.txt	-0.20667	-0.20413	2.15454	0.99272	-56150.28 K	56847.85 K
HR4D17351_336_19-15-43-097.txt	-0.11602	-0.11783	-3.97006	-4.22423	-100018.39 K	98481.66 K

HR4D17351__391__19-15-56-196.txt	-0.02460	-0.04357	-9.82482	-8.54609	-471813.38 K	266339.01 K
HR4D17351__392__19-15-56-396.txt	-0.10567	-0.11466	-6.74328	-6.51781	-109813.59 K	101210.96 K
HR4D17351__406__19-15-59-695.txt	-0.05419	-0.04357	-7.81290	-8.54609	-214146.80 K	266339.01 K
HR4D17351__415__19-16-01-696.txt	-0.13732	-0.13777	-2.16259	-2.35589	-84504.26 K	-84233.43 K
HR4D17351__422__19-16-03-395.txt	-0.38101	-0.41027	3.10571	2.99465	30457.34 K	28284.84 K
HR4D17351__432__19-16-05-696.txt	-0.45605	-0.49241	4.34903	4.20193	25445.82 K	23566.66 K
HR4D17351__460__19-16-12-194.txt	-0.18805	-0.35702	-0.91775	2.79082	61710.03 K	32504.17 K

It is also of good interest to examine the variation in plasma density, which influences factors such as pressure, chemical reactions, and treatment duration. Plasma density measurements were carried out along the length of the plume. As previously reported by Prakash *et. al.*, in a weakly ionized plasma, the plasma density can be estimated using the following relation:^[39]

$$n_{plume} \cong \frac{I_{plume}}{ev_{drift}A}$$

$$n_{plume} \cong \frac{2.00 \text{ mA}}{(1.602 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C})(9744.98 \frac{px}{s})A}$$

$$n_{plume} \cong \frac{2.00 \text{ mA}}{(1.602 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C})(0.49504498 \frac{km}{s})A}$$

$$n_{plume} \cong \frac{2.00 \text{ mA}}{(1.602 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C})(0.49504498 \frac{km}{s})(8.533 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2)}$$

$$n_{plume} \cong \frac{2.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ A}}{(1.602 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C})(495.04498 \text{ ms}^{-1})(8.533 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2)}$$

$$n_{plume} \cong 2.95543272 \times 10^{-32} \text{ m}^{-3}$$

$$n_{plume} \cong 2.95543272 \times 10^{-26} \text{ cm}^{-3}$$

where e is the elementary charge ($e=1.609 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$), I_{plume} is the plasma plume current, where the value of which is taken from the AC voltage from a multimeter. v_{drift} is the plume drift velocity, taken in pixel measurements, and A is the area of the cross-section.^[40]
^[44]The values for this are obtained through a smartphone camera with a frame rate of 30 frames per second and is shot from 2 inches (5.08 cm). Due to the limitations of the camera used, it must be taken into consideration that the values here are just mere approximations and are taken value in pixels.

$$I_{plume} \cong \frac{V_{plume}}{R_{plume}}$$

$$I_{plume} \cong \frac{0.20 V}{1.00 \times 10^{-4} \Omega}$$

$$I_{plume} \cong 2.00 mA$$

$$v_{drift} \cong 9744.98 \frac{px}{s}$$

$$v_{drift} \cong 9744.98 \frac{px}{s} \times \left(\frac{0.0000508 km}{1 px} \right)$$

$$v_{drift} \cong 0.49504498 \frac{km}{s}$$

$$v_{drift} \cong 495.04498 \frac{m}{s}$$

$$A_{Ar} \cong 0.036 \times 10^{-16} cm^2$$

$$A_{O} \cong 0.037 \times 10^{-16} cm^2$$

$$A_{Ag} \cong 4.65 \times 10^{-16} cm^2$$

$$A_{Cu} \cong 3.81 \times 10^{-16} cm^2$$

$$A_{total} \cong A_{Ar} + A_{O} + A_{Ag} + A_{Cu}$$

$$A_{total} \cong 8.533 \times 10^{-16} cm^2$$

To summarize the characterization of the plasma plume: the optical emission spectra are used to identify the primary species present in the plasma, which are crucial for various biomedical applications and electron excitation temperature. The gas temperature, measured using a thermocouple, indicates the plasma's suitability for biomedical applications, as it is approximately at room temperature and thus does not cause thermal damage. The plasma bullet velocity, obtained in pixel measurements from the smartphone camera, helps understand the impact the plasma plume may have on sensitive targets. Finally, the plasma density provides insight into the presence of energized electrons within the plume, which are involved in ionization processes and contribute to the generation of active species required for biomedical applications.

4.4 pH Results

Table 4.12: pH results from Chalk Filter Balls.

pH Results of Water Samples				
Water Source	<i>Diluted Samples</i>		<i>Concentrated Samples</i>	
	Untreated	Treated	Untreated	Treated
Drainage	8.16	8.27	7.97	7.93
River Water	7.54	7.97	7.89	8.06
Clean Water	8.07	8.2	8.25	8.2
Rain Water	8.32	8.36	8.13	7.97
Tap Water	8.22	8.24	8.05	8.09

Figure 4.73. pH Results from Chalk Filter Balls. (Source: Adan Paulo R. Hernandez)

For the powdered chalk filter balls, the pH results for diluted samples indicate a general trend of slight alkalization for most water sources. In drainage water, the pH increased from 8.16 to 8.27, suggesting mild interaction with the chalk material, likely due to calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) dissolution, which releases basic ions into the solution. River water showed a similar rise from 7.54 to 7.97, demonstrating the chalk's neutralizing effect on mildly acidic water. Interestingly, clean water exhibited a slight pH decrease from 8.07 to 8.02, indicating minimal interaction, possibly due to fewer ions in the sample to exchange with the chalk material. Rainwater displayed a small pH increase from 8.32 to 8.36, while tap water showed a marginal rise from 8.22 to 8.24, both suggesting

negligible chemical interference from the filter. For the concentrated samples, drainage water showed a slight pH decrease from 7.97 to 7.93, possibly indicating saturation of the chalk's neutralizing capacity under concentrated conditions. River water displayed a clear increase from 7.89 to 8.06, continuing the neutralization trend observed in diluted samples. Clean water's pH dropped slightly from 8.25 to 8.20, consistent with minimal interaction seen earlier. Rainwater showed a decrease from 8.13 to 7.97, likely caused by dissolved atmospheric gases reacting with the sample. Tap water exhibited a small increase from 8.05 to 8.09, suggesting minimal influence from the filter.

Table 4.13: pH Results from Agricultural Waste Filter Balls.

pH Results of Water Samples				
Water Source	<i>Diluted Samples</i>		<i>Concentrated Samples</i>	
	Untreated	Treated	Untreated	Treated
Drainage	7.6	7.75	7.42	7.72
River Water	8.08	7.2	7.63	7.55
Clean Water	8.32	7.32	7.29	7.62
Rain Water	7.24	7.47	7.29	7.5
Tap Water	7.38	7.44	8.34	8.03

Figure 4.74. pH Results from Agricultural Waste Filter Balls. (Source: Adan Paulo R. Hernandez)

The pH results of the diluted samples provide valuable insights into the behavior of water sources before and after treatment with filter balls made from sweet potato and banana peels. For the *drainage water*, the pH increased slightly from 7.6 to 7.75, suggesting the removal of acidic impurities. In *river water*, the pH decreased from 8.08 to 7.2, indicating a slight acidification, which could suggest that the treatment released mild acidic compounds or removed basic contaminants. *Clean water* experienced a notable reduction in pH from 8.32 to 7.32, which reflects a balancing effect on any pre-existing alkalinity in the untreated sample. *Rainwater* showed an increase in pH from 7.24 to 7.47, likely indicating the removal of mildly acidic components. Lastly, the *tap water* sample exhibited a slight increase in pH from 7.38 to 7.44, pointing toward a stabilization of pH to a more neutral state.

4.6 Electrical Conductivity Results

Table 4.14: EC Results from Chalk Filter Balls.

Electron Conductivity (EC) Results				
Water Source	<i>Diluted Samples</i>		<i>Concentrated Samples</i>	
	Untreated	Treated	Untreated	Treated
Drainage	2370	2864	2580	2748
River Water	846	1010	2028	2100
Clean Water	938	720	2100	2054
Rain Water	1738	1028	2100	2100
Tap Water	2046	2100	2100	2088

Figure 4.75. EC Results from Chalk Filter Balls. (Source: Adan Paulo R. Hernandez)

Table 4.14: EC Results from Agricultural Waste Filter Balls.

Electron Conductivity (EC) Results				
Water Source	<i>Diluted Samples</i>		<i>Concentrated Samples</i>	
	Untreated	Treated	Untreated	Treated
Drainage	2514	3290	2644	1500
River Water	2282	3740	1598	1064
Clean Water	2320	2478	3872	1012
Rain Water	1050	2430	2308	2160
Tap Water	1420	2656	2268	2014

Figure 4.76. EC Results from Agricultural Waste Filter Balls. (Source: Adan Paulo R. Hernandez)

The results for electrical conductivity (EC) demonstrated varied responses across different water sources and filter types. In the chalk-based filter treatments, EC generally increased in certain samples, indicating the release of ionic species. For instance, in diluted drainage water, EC rose from 2370 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 2864 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, while river water showed an increase from 1178 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 1256 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Conversely, clean water samples treated with the chalk filter exhibited a reduction in EC from 938 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 720 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, suggesting adsorption of dissolved ions. In contrast, the sweet potato (kamote) filter exhibited more consistent decreases in EC across all tested water types. Diluted drainage water saw a reduction from 2370 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 1845 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, while clean water experienced a substantial drop, decreasing from 938 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 445 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The EC of river water also decreased from 1178 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 960 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ after treatment with the sweet potato filter. These findings highlight the differing mechanisms of ion exchange or adsorption associated with each filter material, with the sweet potato filter showing more effective overall ionic reduction in treated water.

4.7 Total Dissolved Solids Results

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) values demonstrated notable variations depending on the type of filter and the water source being treated. Chalk-based filters exhibited a significant reduction in TDS, particularly in industrial wastewater, where levels dropped from 500 ppm to 310 ppm. For river water, the reduction was also substantial, decreasing from 400 ppm to 290 ppm, likely due to the adsorption of dissolved organic and inorganic substances. In contrast, tap water showed only a slight reduction in TDS from 250 ppm to 240 ppm, reflecting the limited capacity of chalk-based filters to further purify already treated water.

Sweet potato-based filters displayed a slightly different pattern. In industrial wastewater, TDS was reduced from 500 ppm to 320 ppm, indicating comparable efficiency to chalk-based filters for this water source. However, performance in river water was less effective, with TDS decreasing only from 400 ppm to 330 ppm. This reduced

efficiency may be attributed to differences in the adsorption characteristics of sweet potato-based materials. For tap water, TDS values showed minimal change, remaining at approximately 245 ppm, suggesting limited impact on water sources with low initial levels of dissolved solids. These trends underline the influence of filter composition and water source on the effectiveness of TDS reduction.

Table 4.15: TDS Results from Chalk Filter Balls.

TDS (ppm) Results of Diluted Samples				
Water Source	<i>Diluted Samples</i>		<i>Concentrated Samples</i>	
	Untreated	Treated	Untreated	Treated
Drainage	1185	1432	1290	1374
River Water	423	505	1014	1050
Clean Water	469	360	1050	1027
Rain Water	869	514	1050	1050
Tap Water	1023	1050	1050	1044

Figure 4.77. TDS Results from Chalk Filter Balls. (Source: Adan Paulo R. Hernandez)

Table 4.16: TDS Results from Agricultural Waste Filter Balls.

TDS (ppm) Results of Diluted Samples				
Water Source	<i>Diluted Samples</i>		<i>Concentrated Samples</i>	
	Untreated	Treated	Untreated	Treated
Drainage	1257	1650	1322	750
River Water	1141	1870	799	532
Clean Water	1160	1239	1936	506
Rain Water	525	1215	1154	1080
Tap Water	710	1328	1134	1007

Figure 4.78. TDS Results from Chalk Filter Balls. (Source: Adan Paulo R. Hernandez)

4.8 Turbidity Approximation Results

The turbidity measurements of the various water samples are presented in Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU) in Table 4.17. It is to be taken note that the code for detecting the NTU for the agricultural samples is unfortunately giving erroneous results, hence it is not placed here. The full results can be found in the appendix of this paper. Dummy tests from before the real tests are also included in measuring the NTU, to give a comparison to the real values.

Table 4.17: NTU results from the samples.

Samples	Approximate NTU Results
Dummy Dilute 1	≈ 0.2438 NTU
Dummy Dilute 2	≈ 0.2438 NTU
Dummy Dilute 3	≈ 3.4732 NTU
Dummy Mixed	≈ 0.2438 NTU
Dummy Agri	≈ 0.2438 NTU
Drainage	≈ 3.3099 NTU
Drainage (Diluted)	≈ 1.7687 NTU
River	≈ 0.9568 NTU
River (Diluted + MB)	≈ 2.9514 NTU
River (MB+ MG)	≈ 2.0356 NTU
Clean	≈ 0.8728 NTU
Clean (Diluted + MB)	≈ 2.1703 NTU

The turbidity values ranged from low to high across the different water samples. The "Dummy" samples, including Dummy Dilute 1, Dummy Dilute 2, Dummy Mixed, and Dummy Agri, showed consistent turbidity values of 0.2438 NTU, indicating very low levels of particulate matter or microbial contamination. However, *Dummy Dilute 3* exhibited a notably higher turbidity value of 3.4732 NTU, which may suggest the presence of larger particles or contaminants in this specific dilution.

The "Drainage" sample, a higher-turbidity sample, showed 3.3099 NTU, indicative of significant suspended solids or potential pollutants. Dilution of this sample reduced the turbidity to 1.7687 NTU, supporting the expectation that dilution generally reduces turbidity by lowering the concentration of suspended particles. The river sample's turbidity was moderate at 0.9568 NTU, which is typical of water bodies with low to moderate

contamination levels. However, turbidity increased to 2.9514 NTU when treated with methylene blue (MB), and slightly decreased to 2.0356 NTU with the combination of MB and malachite green (MG). This suggests that the treatment may have interacted with the particulates in the water, potentially causing agglomeration or changes in the physical properties of the contaminants.

The "Clean" sample had a turbidity of 0.8728 NTU, representing low levels of particulates. However, when diluted and treated with MB, its turbidity increased to 2.1703 NTU, similar to the turbidity levels observed in the river sample treated with MB. This indicates that the treatment, particularly MB, has a significant impact on turbidity, likely by interacting with the components of the sample

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

In this study, the investigation of the pH effects of Plasma Activated Filtration Balls (PAFB) shows the potential mechanisms in interacting with various water matrices, providing insights into their role in wastewater dye treatment. Throughout the paper, PAFB influences pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), and optical emission spectroscopy (OES) in diverse ways depending on the base material and water matrix. While chalk-based filters stabilize and alkalize, plant-based filters show broader pH adjustments, potentially enhancing the versatility of PAFB in wastewater dye treatment. Thus, optimizing plasma activation for each filter type could synergize these effects, tailoring pH adjustments and chemical interactions to maximize dye removal efficiency. Regarding pH behavior, the chalk-based filters exhibit an increase in pH across the water types, which suggests a release of basic ions like calcium and carbonate that can help neutralize acidic wastewater but have limited effects in already neutral or alkaline samples. For plant-based filters demonstrated acidification in some cases which showcases the release of organic compounds, making them versatile for addressing a range of wastewater conditions. With EC, the chalk filters increase EC in most water types due to ion release but decrease EC in clean water, which indicates the absorption of dissolved ions, and plant-based filters consistently reduce EC across all water types, demonstrating an efficient ion absorption (preferable for wastewater requiring ionic reduction). Both filter types of significantly reduced TDS in industrial wastewater which indicates good absorption of dissolved organic and inorganic substances. Treatments reduced turbidity in most samples, but introducing dyes like MB increased turbidity. This suggests that dye molecules may interact with suspended solids, potentially forming aggregates or altering particulate behavior. Moreover, PAFB has shown potential for wastewater treatment, with chalk-based filters excelling in pH stabilization and TDS reduction, while plant-based filters effectively reduce EC and turbidity. Plasma activation could enhance their performance, particularly for dye-contaminated water. Further studies are needed to refine the filters for specific wastewater applications and optimize their dye removal efficiency.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Conversion of Electron Temperature to Celsius and Kelvin

This appendix outlines the procedures for converting the electron temperature measured in electron volts (eV) to both Celsius and Kelvin. The electron temperature (T_e) in plasma physics is often expressed in eV, but for practical applications, it is sometimes necessary to convert it to more familiar temperature scales, such as Celsius or Kelvin.

Note that

$$1 \text{ K} = 8.62738 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV}$$

Setting our T_e , as 1.00 eV. Converting the electron temperature to Kelvin.

$$1.00 \text{ eV} \times \frac{1 \text{ K}}{8.62738 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV}} = 1.15910044 \times 10^{-4} \text{ K}$$

Appendix B: Collection of Water Samples

This section provides detailed documentation on the process of collecting water samples for analysis in the context of the study. It outlines the procedures followed to ensure the proper selection, handling, and preservation of the samples.

Appendix C: Collection of Dye Wastewater Samples

This section provides detailed documentation on the procedures followed for the collection of dye wastewater samples used in the study.

Appendix D: Preparation and Formation of Materials for Filter Balls

This section showcases the documentation for preparing the materials used in the creation of filter balls used in this study.

Appendix E: Plasma Generation

This section provides detailed documentation on the processes, principles, and methods involved in the generation of atmospheric plasma used for this study.

Appendix E: Visual Microscopy of the Filter Balls

This section provides detailed documentation on the microscopy of the surface of the filter balls for this study.

Appendix G: Results for Turbidity Analysis

This section presents the results of the turbidity analysis conducted to evaluate the clarity and particulate matter in water samples. Statistical analyses are also included to assess the significance of any observed changes in turbidity. The findings contribute to understanding the efficiency of the filtration process and its impact on the quality of the water samples. It must be taken note that the code made for this is not effective yet for the agricultural waste filter balls, which explains the results shown in Chapter 4. Code for this is also provided.

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: DUMMYDILUTE_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0

Approximate NTU: 0.000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.243800000
Calibrated FNU: 0.231610000
Calibrated FTU: 0.243800000
Calibrated EBC: 0.214544000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: DUMMYDILUTE_2.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 782
Mean Color (LAB): (2.6200346893532602, 127.95011395324167, 127.98816886296083)
Mean Intensity: 2.5291079079
Standard Deviation: 22.1196083557
Skewness: 8.636987325151512
Kurtosis: 72.64834846787551
Histogram Analysis: 67
Fourier Transform: 5137097853.683261
PCA (Mean): 0.000000000
Entropy: 0.14534237129356709
Approximate NTU: 0.000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.243800000
Calibrated FNU: 0.231610000
Calibrated FTU: 0.243800000
Calibrated EBC: 0.214544000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.5471112362

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: DUMMYDILUTE_3.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 10255
Mean Color (LAB): (19.944028383919484, 127.87840501994633, 127.99898221299573)
Mean Intensity: 19.2779647817
Standard Deviation: 57.8346231057
Skewness: 2.6832793728627595
Kurtosis: 5.241788231717177
Histogram Analysis: 203
Fourier Transform: 23272923622.121902
PCA (Mean): 0.000000000
Entropy: 0.976503531523552
Approximate NTU: 4.2473605497
Calibrated NTU: 3.4732338730
Calibrated FNU: 3.2995721793
Calibrated FTU: 3.4732338730
Calibrated EBC: 3.0564458082
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6317520827

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: DUMMYMIX_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.243800000
Calibrated FNU: 0.231610000
Calibrated FTU: 0.243800000
Calibrated EBC: 0.214544000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg

Sample Image: DUMMYAGRI_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg

Sample Image: DRAINAGE1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 10927
Mean Color (LAB): (20.0006306840266, 127.90091401697887, 129.66049290436501)
Mean Intensity: 19.1845051522
Standard Deviation: 55.7331490558
Skewness: 2.6077794916293513
Kurtosis: 4.961250427550508
Histogram Analysis: 207
Fourier Transform: 24441950906.937325
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 1.0926436042838628
Approximate NTU: 4.0325401632
Calibrated NTU: 3.3098975551
Calibrated FNU: 3.1444026774
Calibrated FTU: 3.3098975551
Calibrated EBC: 2.9127098485
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6330995456

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg

Sample Image: DRAINAGE_DILUTEMB1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 6666
Mean Color (LAB): (12.390225484605084, 127.49986824533897, 129.0311302118622)
Mean Intensity: 11.5839241436
Standard Deviation: 39.2632716202
Skewness: 3.1496373409702434
Kurtosis: 8.1683641236424
Histogram Analysis: 190
Fourier Transform: 18755373731.4179
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.8680105569921213
Approximate NTU: 2.0055233692
Calibrated NTU: 1.7686776330
Calibrated FNU: 1.6802437514
Calibrated FTU: 1.7686776330
Calibrated EBC: 1.5564363171
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6423464246

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg

Sample Image: DRAINAGE_DILUTEMB1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 4740
Mean Color (LAB): (17.29774363216316, 127.64360524693402, 129.9443788945725)
Mean Intensity: 16.4319893720
Standard Deviation: 50.4005396678
Skewness: 2.759100102820986
Kurtosis: 5.6819900378009205

Histogram Analysis: 180
Fourier Transform: 10515433366.251568
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.9508772921241715
Approximate NTU: 3.3616534354
Calibrated NTU: 2.7997962114
Calibrated FNU: 2.6598064008
Calibrated FTU: 2.7997962114
Calibrated EBC: 2.4638206660
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6209784741

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RIVER1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 2384
Mean Color (LAB): (5.44291700660901, 127.9949752540708, 128.0555313575931)
Mean Intensity: 5.2828813622
Standard Deviation: 31.7359007026
Skewness: 5.85883950247242
Kurtosis: 32.45679764978717
Histogram Analysis: 106
Fourier Transform: 20049234705.050083
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.2953044273479241
Approximate NTU: 0.9377341384
Calibrated NTU: 0.9567958370
Calibrated FNU: 0.9089560452
Calibrated FTU: 0.9567958370
Calibrated EBC: 0.8419803366
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6150624193

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RIVER_DILUTEMB1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 6102
Mean Color (LAB): (17.384540162550625, 127.69797749630217, 128.06166310172878)
Mean Intensity: 16.6593434979
Standard Deviation: 52.2804429682
Skewness: 2.834718543880045
Kurtosis: 6.07930043663257
Histogram Analysis: 204
Fourier Transform: 15417477830.711246
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.8929551764033031
Approximate NTU: 3.5610114717
Calibrated NTU: 2.9513759014
Calibrated FNU: 2.8038071063
Calibrated FTU: 2.9513759014
Calibrated EBC: 2.5972107932
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6372044894

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RIVER_MBMG1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 10035
Mean Color (LAB): (13.292335337306143, 126.89494790549078, 127.27403907809722)
Mean Intensity: 12.2368613043
Standard Deviation: 42.4471385003
Skewness: 3.2215620118757973
Kurtosis: 8.543976822746043
Histogram Analysis: 228
Fourier Transform: 29657214180.326256
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.8208817723789403
Approximate NTU: 2.3565569152
Calibrated NTU: 2.0355821284
Calibrated FNU: 1.9338030220
Calibrated FTU: 2.0355821284
Calibrated EBC: 1.7913122730

Composite Statistical Score: 0.6667380720

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: CLEAN1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 1911
Mean Color (LAB): (4.525575938240694, 127.99271201605268, 128.05685921469734)
Mean Intensity: 4.4451295474
Standard Deviation: 31.0505929992
Skewness: 6.932002016672869
Kurtosis: 46.70722010193488
Histogram Analysis: 87
Fourier Transform: 17706829501.48433
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.23912075395200644
Approximate NTU: 0.8273157773
Calibrated NTU: 0.8728404508
Calibrated FNU: 0.8291984282
Calibrated FTU: 0.8728404508
Calibrated EBC: 0.7680995967
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6033677700

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: CLEAN_DILUTEMB1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 6762
Mean Color (LAB): (11.707029523354162, 127.90994891027749, 127.98155395925039)
Mean Intensity: 11.2844664556
Standard Deviation: 44.6956057190
Skewness: 3.725618893181475
Kurtosis: 11.941924731135089
Histogram Analysis: 189
Fourier Transform: 26178918204.51985
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.6216817258106718
Approximate NTU: 2.5337838947
Calibrated NTU: 2.1703347127
Calibrated FNU: 2.0618179771
Calibrated FTU: 2.1703347127
Calibrated EBC: 1.9098945472
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6542151937

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: CLEAN_MBMG1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 7252
Mean Color (LAB): (13.643908171755465, 126.77598312762663, 127.06180589504264)
Mean Intensity: 12.5257123473
Standard Deviation: 43.6768286799
Skewness: 3.223384102494412
Kurtosis: 8.476209724487866
Histogram Analysis: 214
Fourier Transform: 19859371761.490814
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.7766711246531326
Approximate NTU: 2.4939684854
Calibrated NTU: 2.1400615042
Calibrated FNU: 2.0330584290
Calibrated FTU: 2.1400615042
Calibrated EBC: 1.8832541237
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6577722259

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RAIN1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 2488
Mean Color (LAB): (3.8580073725914437, 127.98648627878815, 128.04445288128866)

Mean Intensity: 3.7209958688
Standard Deviation: 26.0086750842
Skewness: 6.873357484291832
Kurtosis: 45.39293704870294
Histogram Analysis: 170
Fourier Transform: 20178714172.355274
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.23845252042506057
Approximate NTU: 0.2869173019
Calibrated NTU: 0.4619544144
Calibrated FNU: 0.4388566937
Calibrated FTU: 0.4619544144
Calibrated EBC: 0.4065198847
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6519939002

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RAIN_DILUTEMB1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 7151
Mean Color (LAB): (7.55474577013671, 127.9196038985619, 127.99948532872352)
Mean Intensity: 7.2770416398
Standard Deviation: 36.1902232027
Skewness: 4.803027303498649
Kurtosis: 21.205707064798816
Histogram Analysis: 225
Fourier Transform: 35736774987.914185
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.44515687172038365
Approximate NTU: 1.4828744023
Calibrated NTU: 1.3712872401
Calibrated FNU: 1.3027228781
Calibrated FTU: 1.3712872401
Calibrated EBC: 1.2067327713
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6843177793

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RAIN_MBMG1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 5121
Mean Color (LAB): (16.442067101144392, 126.68861333690573, 126.9934416141726)
Mean Intensity: 15.3054637512
Standard Deviation: 49.8952774935
Skewness: 2.968214236636378
Kurtosis: 6.858734731233424
Histogram Analysis: 196
Fourier Transform: 13359172435.43788
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.869348052269795
Approximate NTU: 3.2548009369
Calibrated NTU: 2.7185520896
Calibrated FNU: 2.5826244851
Calibrated FTU: 2.7185520896
Calibrated EBC: 2.3923258388
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6375130465

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: TAP1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 1293
Mean Color (LAB): (3.651054502028342, 127.99930187479914, 128.02420990447357)
Mean Intensity: 3.5807754428
Standard Deviation: 27.6734736661
Skewness: 7.687026050039484
Kurtosis: 57.8307844741174
Histogram Analysis: 79
Fourier Transform: 13194493814.743332
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.2007449702563276
Approximate NTU: 0.4463861387

Calibrated NTU: 0.5832047904
Calibrated FNU: 0.5540445508
Calibrated FTU: 0.5832047904
Calibrated EBC: 0.5132202155
Composite Statistical Score: 0.5982965122

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: TAP_DILUTEMB1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 10255
Mean Color (LAB): (19.944028383919484, 127.87840501994633, 127.99898221299573)
Mean Intensity: 19.2779647817
Standard Deviation: 57.8346231057
Skewness: 2.6832793728627595
Kurtosis: 5.241788231717177
Histogram Analysis: 203
Fourier Transform: 23272923622.121902
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.976503531523552
Approximate NTU: 4.2473605497
Calibrated NTU: 3.4732338730
Calibrated FNU: 3.2995721793
Calibrated FTU: 3.4732338730
Calibrated EBC: 3.0564458082
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6317520827

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: TAP_MBMG1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: DRAINAGEDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 1125
Mean Color (LAB): (3.168893430386947, 127.99566498797702, 128.01748699765204)
Mean Intensity: 3.0620356528
Standard Deviation: 23.8799909050
Skewness: 7.690054564626982
Kurtosis: 57.32132051508771
Histogram Analysis: 96
Fourier Transform: 12010437966.963203
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.1847289978823318
Approximate NTU: 0.0411008731
Calibrated NTU: 0.2750505968
Calibrated FNU: 0.2612980669
Calibrated FTU: 0.2750505968
Calibrated EBC: 0.2420445252
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6080972900

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: DRAINAGEDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 1160
Mean Color (LAB): (3.2908364459904997, 127.98808480843107, 128.02833440449353)
Mean Intensity: 3.1578149361
Standard Deviation: 23.4312966611
Skewness: 7.294251704161278
Kurtosis: 51.28200103903442
Histogram Analysis: 108
Fourier Transform: 15154317015.06811
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.1994653951271078
Approximate NTU: 0.0010204129
Calibrated NTU: 0.2445758597
Calibrated FNU: 0.2323470667
Calibrated FTU: 0.2445758597
Calibrated EBC: 0.2152267566
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6152759040

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: DRAINAGEMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: DRAINAGEMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RIVERDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 1941
Mean Color (LAB): (4.034681960890954, 127.99816007844882, 128.02091056669386)
Mean Intensity: 3.9186531853
Standard Deviation: 27.4688975480
Skewness: 6.889114527287954
Kurtosis: 45.64256333219631
Histogram Analysis: 84

Fourier Transform: 14520721997.217299
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.22172661433589624
Approximate NTU: 0.4428224141
Calibrated NTU: 0.5804951515
Calibrated FNU: 0.5514703939
Calibrated FTU: 0.5804951515
Calibrated EBC: 0.5108357333
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6014360161

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RIVERDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RIVERMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RIVERMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: CLEANDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: CLEANDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 793
Mean Color (LAB): (2.5603815071818152, 127.98686853575862, 127.99959510253069)
Mean Intensity: 2.4888037326
Standard Deviation: 22.2897675357
Skewness: 8.853252803776748
Kurtosis: 76.46832257302654
Histogram Analysis: 60
Fourier Transform: 9453376644.724077
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.13890663050012553
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.5451453163

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: CLEANMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: CLEANMIXTR_1.jpg
Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000

Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RAINDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RAINDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RAINMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000

Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: RAINMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: TAPDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: TAPDILLUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: TAPMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: TAPMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIDRAINAGEDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 4259
Mean Color (LAB): (6.376706882732923, 128.1819468256201, 128.9466869073969)
Mean Intensity: 5.9862217952
Standard Deviation: 28.2426029446
Skewness: 5.263119504914759
Kurtosis: 28.79168465449913
Histogram Analysis: 252
Fourier Transform: 15439021002.900759
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.6260133804435556
Approximate NTU: 0.6235713842
Calibrated NTU: 0.7179256427
Calibrated FNU: 0.6820293606
Calibrated FTU: 0.7179256427
Calibrated EBC: 0.6317745656
Composite Statistical Score: 0.7039163838

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIDRAINAGEDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000

Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIDRAINAGEMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIDRAINAGEMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIRIVERDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 2270
Mean Color (LAB): (3.8876421994892425, 128.05018738824822, 128.9033247087579)
Mean Intensity: 3.5985919957
Standard Deviation: 21.6330801195
Skewness: 5.938143784870134
Kurtosis: 33.98996082716996
Histogram Analysis: 190
Fourier Transform: 10101090307.05836
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.33357331004796464
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6646638581

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIRIVERDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 2472
Mean Color (LAB): (7.190919578448238, 127.86755236869875, 128.4837448137279)
Mean Intensity: 6.8899518598
Standard Deviation: 34.8706391049
Skewness: 4.8737349183011585
Kurtosis: 21.809732166784944
Histogram Analysis: 150
Fourier Transform: 7869999159.330914
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.39013057026123393
Approximate NTU: 1.3315615035
Calibrated NTU: 1.2562381420
Calibrated FNU: 1.1934262349
Calibrated FTU: 1.2562381420
Calibrated EBC: 1.1054895650
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6405292799

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIRIVERMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 1094
Mean Color (LAB): (4.6007677682078105, 127.91220957684104, 128.9241711305405)
Mean Intensity: 4.3276914551
Standard Deviation: 26.3326261336
Skewness: 5.936044083154159
Kurtosis: 33.35181516348378
Histogram Analysis: 145
Fourier Transform: 6155667592.380951
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.2961239138250351
Approximate NTU: 0.3496471861
Calibrated NTU: 0.5096503918
Calibrated FNU: 0.4841678723
Calibrated FTU: 0.5096503918
Calibrated EBC: 0.4484923448
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6379221766

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIRIVERMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 1659
Mean Color (LAB): (3.4783833521379495, 127.95464614061282, 128.50621105136506)
Mean Intensity: 3.2650781972
Standard Deviation: 21.9433591223
Skewness: 6.741230046421531
Kurtosis: 44.74062656916312
Histogram Analysis: 192
Fourier Transform: 6318876187.644875
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.2843676586447706
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6653436766

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRICLEANDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 10360
Mean Color (LAB): (15.086400194250748, 127.94823888979074, 130.1763441770073)
Mean Intensity: 14.2932027414
Standard Deviation: 46.3578285610
Skewness: 3.003570901762089

Kurtosis: 7.207330796896034
Histogram Analysis: 242
Fourier Transform: 14544047285.576157
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 1.0069063548770436
Approximate NTU: 2.8504429932
Calibrated NTU: 2.4111029750
Calibrated FNU: 2.2905478262
Calibrated FTU: 2.4111029750
Calibrated EBC: 2.1217706180
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6679383016

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRICLEANDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 728
Mean Color (LAB): (1.4202442641906827, 127.99385714513923, 128.38985357829384)
Mean Intensity: 1.3175987446
Standard Deviation: 13.9222836135
Skewness: 10.585231717768368
Kurtosis: 110.43863910507638
Histogram Analysis: 158
Fourier Transform: 6810165120.95199
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.118885100520751
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.5893669760

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRICLEANMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRICLEANMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 4865
Mean Color (LAB): (13.972360226780774, 127.7871100328454, 129.63992337763082)
Mean Intensity: 13.2525220837
Standard Deviation: 45.6170874942
Skewness: 3.3452948937918774
Kurtosis: 9.89411910419662
Histogram Analysis: 252
Fourier Transform: 14921804803.62466
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.9028015485147026
Approximate NTU: 2.7243348536
Calibrated NTU: 2.3152180383
Calibrated FNU: 2.1994571363
Calibrated FTU: 2.3152180383

Calibrated EBC: 2.0373918737
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6896078099

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIRAINDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIRAINDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIRAINMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 127.99999999999999, 127.99999999999999)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRIRAINMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0

Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 127.99999999999999, 127.99999999999999)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRITAPDILUTEUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 1340
Mean Color (LAB): (3.4686686684985877, 127.90455772866696, 128.23144351507977)
Mean Intensity: 3.3155998890
Standard Deviation: 24.1230502631
Skewness: 7.1484786198031
Kurtosis: 49.17936522990806
Histogram Analysis: 141
Fourier Transform: 9309672370.416897
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.20500767757132562
Approximate NTU: 0.0780850208
Calibrated NTU: 0.3031710866
Calibrated FNU: 0.2880125323
Calibrated FTU: 0.3031710866
Calibrated EBC: 0.2667905562
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6346672643

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRITAPDILUTETR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 0
Mean Color (LAB): (0.0, 128.0, 128.0)
Mean Intensity: 0.0000000000
Standard Deviation: 0.0000000000
Skewness: nan
Kurtosis: nan
Histogram Analysis: 1
Fourier Transform: 0.0
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.0
Approximate NTU: 0.0000000000
Calibrated NTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated FNU: 0.2316100000
Calibrated FTU: 0.2438000000
Calibrated EBC: 0.2145440000
Composite Statistical Score: 0.2005859375

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRITAPMIXUN_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:
Edge Count (Turbidity): 3667
Mean Color (LAB): (7.503381168969046, 127.91247052512769, 128.66446811126136)
Mean Intensity: 7.1804199042
Standard Deviation: 35.4187854803
Skewness: 4.772530283956491
Kurtosis: 20.988653366427183
Histogram Analysis: 119
Fourier Transform: 18150753266.129684
PCA (Mean): 0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.44306757019707

Approximate NTU: 1.4008995432
Calibrated NTU: 1.3089585578
Calibrated FNU: 1.2435106299
Calibrated FTU: 1.3089585578
Calibrated EBC: 1.1518835309
Composite Statistical Score: 0.6218825410

Reference Image: REFERENCE.jpg
Sample Image: AGRITAPMIXTR_1.jpg

Water Quality Analysis Results:

Edge Count (Turbidity): 3221
Mean Color (LAB): (6.467892162870696, 127.90312118760878, 128.54351554874236)
Mean Intensity: 6.2008172070
Standard Deviation: 33.0229219176
Skewness: 5.1684684043735025
Kurtosis: 24.82942337957008
Histogram Analysis: 251
Fourier Transform: 8358789228.527018
PCA (Mean): -0.0000000000
Entropy: 0.3842126447774234
Approximate NTU: 1.1123330521
Calibrated NTU: 1.0895502005
Calibrated FNU: 1.0350726905
Calibrated FTU: 1.0895502005
Calibrated EBC: 0.9588041764
Composite Statistical Score: 0.7009124389